

Interview Questions

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) [1] is a highly regarded model in the field of technology acceptance research. Its primary aim is to explain and predict user acceptance and usage behavior towards information technologies. The UTAUT model can be applied to understand and analyze the adoption of PM to discover RPA/AAI automation opportunities by focusing on the following four key constructs: Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, Social Influence, and Facilitating Conditions.

Simple and non-reidentifying demographic questions will first be asked at the beginning:

1) Demographic Questions

- Is your organization in the private sector, or in the public sector?
- In which country do you practice?
- What is your title or generic role in your organization?
- How many years of experience do you have using:
 - Process Mining (PM)?
 - Robotic Process Automation (RPA)?
 - Agentic AI (AAI)?

Then, UTAUT-inspired and complementary questions will be asked:

2) General Context

- What goals do you typically consider when automating a process or part thereof?
- What process discovery techniques do you use to understand the process that is being automated?
- How do you identify RPA/AAI automation opportunities in processes?
- How do you monitor the performance of RPA bots and AI Agents once deployed?

3) Performance Expectancy

- How effective do you believe Process Mining is in identifying potential areas for RPA/AAI-based activity automation?
- How can Process Mining impact the speed and accuracy of finding RPA/AAI automation opportunities?
- How do you compare the utility of PM with other methods to identify automation opportunities?

4) Effort Expectancy

- How easy or difficult was it to learn how to use Process Mining tools?
- What challenges, if any, did you face when interacting with these technologies for the first time?
- How much effort do you need to invest to use these technologies effectively in your role?

5) Social Influence

- How often do colleagues or leaders recommend using PM to identify automation opportunities (RPA or AAI)?
- Does senior management actively support the use of new technologies such as PM in your role?

6) Facilitating Conditions

- Do you have access to the resources needed to use PM and automation tools effectively?
- How well are you supported by IT or other departments when using these tools?
- Have you received training or guidance on how to use these tools?

7) Behavioral Intention

- If you are already using PM to identify RPA/AAI opportunities:
 1. How likely are you to continue doing so in the future, and why?
 2. What would prevent you from continuing?
- If you are not already using PM to identify RPA/AAI opportunities:
 1. How likely are you to incorporate PM for this purpose in the future, and why?
 2. What would motivate you to prioritize PM in your strategy for automation discovery?
 3. Are you willing to invest time and effort in mastering PM tools to improve RPA/AAI automation outcomes?

References

[1] Andreas Chang. *UTAUT and UTAUT 2: A review and agenda for future research*. The Winners, 13(2):106–114, September 2012. doi: 10.21512/tw.v13i2.656.